

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Abbas**FIRST NAME:** Tanveer**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 8%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 Professional Plus on Windows 11 Home)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In essay writing, the first step is to produce the draft according to the structure and framework of the essay. The details of the essay will become much simpler once you have a draft. Format for the structure of the essay to be followed is:-

- Introduction, Body, and Conclusion.**¹
- Abstract, Body, and Recommendations.
- Introduction, Problem of Statement, and Conclusion.
- Body, Recommendations, and Conclusion.

2. Which one of them does not fall into the ambit of plagiarism?

- Words of another author.
- Ideas of another author.

¹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2022), 10.

Common Knowledge.²

Statistics/ Data from an organization.

3. Which one of them is not one of the kinds of sources?

Primary Sources.

Secondary Sources.

Original Sources.³

Tertiary Sources.

4. There are a variety of sources of potential bias in dissertation research. The bias stemming from personal experience using interventions in practice, leading to perceptions of the perceived effectiveness or ineffectiveness of a specific strategy of service delivery intervention is called:-

Theory Bias.

Experience Bias.

Intervention Bias.⁴

Funding Bias.

² Laurent and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 34-39.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 35–36.

⁴ James P Sampson, Jr, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second (Tallahassee: The Florida State University, 2017), 8–9.

5. Conducting dissertation research involves preparing two to four documents. Ideally, students prepare the following four dissertation documents:-

Concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript.⁵

Introduction, prospectus, dissertation, and manuscript.

Concept paper, prospectus, dissertation, and conclusion.

Introduction, prospectus, dissertation, and conclusion.

6. Every question which expects a separate answer should be followed by a question mark. Which statement out of the following is incorrect with regards to the usage of question mark:-

There should be no space between the question mark and the preceding word, letter, or number.

A question mark is used at the end of a direct question.

Question marks are not used in indirect speech.

Always use a question mark after a request or instruction disguised as a question out of courtesy.⁶

7. There are three kinds of sources, i.e., primary, secondary, and tertiary. Which one of the following statements is true with regards to the sources:-

Tertiary sources are books and articles that analyze the primary sources.

⁵ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2.

⁶ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth (European Commission, 2021), 13.

- Primary sources are based on secondary sources, usually written by non-specialists.
 - Primary sources consist of diaries, letters, manuscripts, images, films, film scripts, recordings, and musical scores created by writers, artists, and composers.⁷**
 - Primary sources are used for three purposes, i.e., keeping with current research, finding other points of view, and finding models for your analysis and point of view.
8. Which of the following statements is true regarding the citation of sources? We cite to:-
- Give credit.
 - Assure accuracy.
 - Show research traditions.
 - All of the above.⁸**
9. Which of the following best describes the purpose of a statement of the problem in a research proposal?
- To articulate the researcher's personal interest in the topic.
 - To summarize existing literature related to the research area.
 - To clearly define the gap or issue that the research aims to address.⁹**

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 35–37.

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 139–41.

To outline the methodology and data collection techniques.

10. In writing the conclusion of a PhD thesis, which of the following strategies is most effective for ensuring academic rigor and completeness?

Highlighting the limitations of the study and proposing potential areas for further research.¹⁰

Synthesizing the main findings and proposing theoretical extensions based on personal insights.

Including a detailed critique of the methodologies used and their implications for future research.

Exploring the ethical considerations involved in the study and their impact on the research outcomes.

⁹ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth (Los Angeles, California: The Columbia University, 2019), 308–314.

¹⁰ Laurent and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 10.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth ed. European Commission, 2021.

Laurent, Cleenewerck, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth. Bangui: Euclid University, 2022.

Linda Dale, Bloomberg, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. Los Angeles, California: The Columbia University, 2019.

Sampson, Jr, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Tallahassee: The Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed.. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.